

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-8

USE OF DIFFERENT ENERGY SOURCES IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF BUILDINGS

Kuchkarbaev Rustam Utkurovich

Doctor of Philosophy of Pedagogical Sciences, PhD.

Abstract: This article presents methods of using various energy sources in the construction processes of buildings in the conditions of modern Uzbekistan. In the article, energy sources are the types of them, buildings are being constructed in the process of using the main differences, advantages and disadvantages given.

Key words: Energy, solar, panel, reserve, building, structure, process, system, natural, air, conductor, water, battery, supply, collector.

Solar heating system (SHT) is distinguished by active and passive systems. A characteristic feature of an active QIT is that the solar energy collector (QEK) has a heat accumulator (IA), an additional (reserve) energy source (QEM), heat exchangers (in double-circuit systems), a pump or fan, coupling or air transmitters, control systems are also available.

In the case of passive systems, the barrier structures of the building serve as a thermal power plant and heat storage, and the transfer of air heated by solar energy is usually carried out due to natural convection. In passive systems, sunlight entering the building through large windows is designed to be directly captured by the south-facing walls and floor of the building, the amount of heat collected and stored depending on the mass of the walls, floor and water tank. or a device installed on the south side of the building, depending on the quantity and quality of the heat transfer device into the building.

From the experience and analysis of the use of passive solar heating systems in the conditions of Uzbekistan, the following conclusions can be drawn :

1. Directly sun radiation transition system efficiency is low. Winter during the addition of a heating source requires summer while the room is hot;
2. Large massive heating to the batteries have been indirect or insulated heating methods used to the purpose in accordance with
3. Return and screening from systems when used, the efficiency increases more, that is, in summer the Sun radiation passing into the building decreases in the winter in the daytime season, while the Sun radiation passing through increases at night and heat loss decreases;
4. Uzbekistan conditions for a passive heating system for the necessary heating (30... 60) % of the amount that the Sun can cover with energy

Night or sun did not happen trash can at times heat up no tooth reduce for trash can light return to surface heat catch heat protector with (fence , fence and others) will also change recommendation needs to be done can

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-8

Figure 1. Passive solar system with heated building window south side and heat accumulator wall between air natural circular t political 1-building , 2-heat collector, 3-window.

Traceability level burden there was sunshine many n in quantity was And external hav o'arta I'm yours will be in the regions passive Sun With heating system windows when And bin on the floor And ceiling between air circulation For y e tarli oh ralik When heat ' mask' efficiency burden will be (picture 1). In this electronic control system f about idali Job coefficient up to 40 % death B can Passive from QIT when using , heat up the trash can because of relationship quality , warmth save get up requirements I'm in about be ready too much e'tib or r be ready what kind of cancer.

The current sun is active at this time from systems greater than q is used. KEK (all energy collector) o ' s in general terms heat transport w feature looking liquid and air can be systematic can in KEK heat the carrier is a liquid or water be possible, including 40-50% ethylene or propylene glycol solution gaseous resin organic heat carrier and another can Heat carriers each one known advantages and due to ns have maybe For example, when using air, freeze and rust from the problem, the solution will be, the device softens the mass, liquid heat the carrier leak from the output visible damage eliminate does That's why for both water that's all up to time In the QIT devices used, most heating takes place. serves as a heat carrier.

Figure 2 . Schematic diagram of a solar air heating system. 1- Sun energy collection , 2 - gravel to heat the battery, 3 - fan , 4 - speaker parts, 5 - addition to heat the source.

2 and 3 have o and water from the operating Sun systems are given structural diagrams . The bin o inside the Sun system, thermal ventilation system with heating together placed on the distribution board will be.

Solar devices for building heating and hot water supply can be included in the combined solar fuel system of heat transfer, and it is possible to fully cover the annual heat needs of the consumer at the expense of solar energy. The reserve source of heat should serve to fully cover the heat needs of the destination. In some cases, it is possible to use the solar devices in an incomplete amount and store the rest in reserve. For this purpose, the buildings should fully meet the modern requirements of heat saving and energy storage, and all its elements, especially solar equipment, should be carefully designed. The highest level of solar energy use efficiency can be achieved if all the listed conditions are fully observed.

Flat (without concentration) sun devices such as sun , heat carrier from 100° C every time It is widely used in uncomplicated cases. Such sun devices, as o san , hot water and other in appearance heat die is used for this purpose.

Figure 3 . Scheme of the liquid solar system for heating and hot water supply. 1- Sun energy collection , 2- The sun in the energy collection circuit heats the heat exchanger, 3- heat accumulator, 4- additional most energy source, 5- bin o , 6- us o s, 7- mixer tap, 8- hot water in the supply chain heat the changer.

Device Sun energy collection, hot water battery or tank and connection from the pipes will be a lesson. Water battery look this is from the bottom water is supplied from above this is silent hot water is transferred.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED

1. Қахҳоров С.К., Самиев К.А., Жўраев Ҳ.О. Қуёш қурилмаларидаги жараёнларни моделлаштириш. Монография. – Тошкент: ИТА PRESS, 2014. – 208 б.
2. Duffie J., Beckman W. Solar engineering of thermal processes. – New York. Wiley, 1991. – 919 p.
3. Jo'rayev T.D. Quyosh issiqlik qurilmalari. O'quv qo'llanma. – Buxoro: Dizayn-Press, 2012. – 107 b.
4. Qahhorov S.Q., Jo'rayev H.O. Fizika ta'limida geliotexnologiya. – T.: Fan, 2009. – 191 b.
5. Qahhorov S.Q., Jo'rayev H.O., Jamilov Y.Y., Hamdamova N.M. Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalari. – Buxoro: Durdona, 2021. – 224 b.
6. Xayriddinov B.E., Xolmirzayev N.S., Sattorov B.N. Quyosh energiyasidan foydalanishning fizik asoslari. O'quv-uslubiy qo'llanma. – T.: Fan, 2011. – 240 b.
7. G'aniyev A.G., Avliyoqulov A.K., Almardanova G.A. Fizika, I qism: Akademik litseylar va kasb-hunar kollejlari uchun darslik. –T.: "O'qituvchi" NMIU, 2005. – 384 b.
8. <http://www.aenergy.ru>
9. <http://www.altenergy.narod.ru>